

BARRIERS TO ONLINE LEARNING DURING THE PANDEMIC: A SURVEY OF NURSING STUDENTS IN AN ALLIED MEDICAL HEALTH SCIENCE SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic had forced schools all around the Philippines to abruptly stop face to face activities and shifted to online learning. This study aimed to identify barriers to online learning of nursing students from an allied medical health science school. Using an electronic survey questionnaire, the following data were obtained: Demographic, Family Income, and the Barriers to Online Learning. The study utilized Percentage, Mean, Frequency, Likert Scale, Standard Deviation, Chi Square, and Pearson-r correlation to interpret results. Among the 79 respondents, 100% fall within the age category of adults, 65.8 % are female, 88.6% are Roman Catholics, and 45.6% have a family income ranging P26,000-P35,000. The age variable had a significant relationship with all the barriers to online learning. Technological barriers obtained a mean of 3.18, while Individual Barriers obtained 4.01. Course Curriculum barriers obtained a mean of 3.74, while Domestic obtained 3.34. Institutional barriers obtained a 3.31 mean, while Community gained 3.77. Based on these results, the respondents Agree that Individual, Course Curriculum, and Community barriers affect online learning. On the other hand, they were unsure whether Technological, Institutional, and Domestic barriers affect online learning. In conclusion, the nursing students confronted several barriers as they tried to adapt to the online learning setup

Keywords: *Barriers, Online Learning, Pandemic, Nursing*

INTRODUCTION

In March 2020, the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic forced medical schools in the Philippines to stop face-to-face learning activities and abruptly shift to an online curriculum (Baticulon MD et al., 2021). Halfway into the second semester, medical schools had to cease all face-to-face learning activities. Nursing students were removed from clinics, wards, intensive care units, and emergency departments. Local and international electives were cancelled. The national internship program was likewise suspended, and the physician licensure exam postponed indefinitely. Forced to abruptly transition to an online curriculum, each nursing school crafted its own guidelines on learning activities, revised assessment measures, and set promotion policies.

In low- and middle-income countries, online learning has the potential to (1) address faculty shortage, expanding the reach of nursing educators and improving their efficiency; (2) improve access to health professions' training, increasing the number of health workers and encouraging their retention in regional units; and (3) facilitate collaboration with institutions that have more resources (Frehywot S et al., 2013). Although online education is well recognized and documented as a promising and effective mode for teaching undergraduate nursing students (McCutcheon, 2014), it was a different story to conduct fully online courses during the COVID-19 crisis, as the online courses' function and people's mental states can be very different from those during ordinary times.

With the end view of aiding the students in their learning and the continuous improvement of this learning platform (Shawaqfeh et al., 2020), properly identifying learning challenges and addressing their particular obstacles in distance online education are necessary (Muilenburg & Berge, 2005). Therefore, it is imperative and urgent to understand and identify the barriers of online courses for this group of nursing students in Doña Remedios Trinidad Romualdez Medical Foundation.

As the great technological advancement has raised our standard of living especially during this pandemic, it brought a huge impact on everyone's life. The COVID-19 has resulted in schools to temporarily close all across the world and everyone has shifted to online and distance learning. Before the pandemic, the use of language applications, virtual tutoring, video conferencing tools, or learning online learning software has grown significantly. The sudden spread of the virus has made everyone transfer and adjust to the "new normal" set-up in daily lives, particularly in education.

Starting from the first two months of the pandemic, almost every country in the world decided to temporarily close each educational institution to contain the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic and the hope of reducing the infections (UNESCO, 2020). The

aftermath of this closure has affected more than 1.2 billion learners worldwide with more than 28 million learners in the Philippines (UNESCO, 2020).

Research Objectives

The researchers' primary objective is to identify barriers to online learning in time of COVID-19 to the nursing students in Doña Remedios Trinidad Romualdez Medical Foundation. It emphasizes the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. The researchers also aim to understand and utilize the best methods and modes to engage and motivate the respondents to online learning to the current situation. This seeks to gather information from the respondents by asking about the research, which will give sufficient answers and details about the barriers to online learning and explore the reflection results of the nursing students in Doña Remedios Trinidad Romualdez Medical Foundation to the online learning process in time of COVID-19.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used cross sectional research design as it gathered the data in which only a small group of people is selected from a given population. This type of design provided information on the prevalence of outcomes of online learning and how it affects the quality of education and also it attempted to determine the relationships between sociodemographic profile and the barriers to online learning, which was important in the cohort research design. Data was gathered through approaches other than questionnaires such as platforms like google forms, messenger and google mail.

Moreover, this study used the quantitative method to explore the research questions as it allowed researchers to describe and interpret objects statistically with numbers.

Research Environment

The study conducted the selected second year nursing students of a highly urbanized city as respondents. There are 99 students and through a random sampling, a number of chosen respondents answered the survey questionnaires through an online platform. This type of research environment was selected by the researchers for economical and accessibility reasons.

Research Respondents and Target Population

The target population of the study belonged among the level 2 nursing students of a particular institution in a highly urbanized city. The researchers selected the respondents from this year level because they were among the only batches who experienced online learning fully. The selection of the research participants was done

using random sampling. There are 79 respondents taken based on the computation of slovin formula.

Research Instrument

The study used a survey instrument adopted from the study of author Baticulon, et al., 2021 to gather the needed data. It is divided into two sections: Part I provides information on the profile of selected level two nursing students in a highly urbanized city. It includes the profile variables in the study such as age, gender, and socio-economic status (eg. family income). Part II congregates information in determining the barriers of online learning to the selected second year nursing students in different categories. This includes technological barriers, individual barriers, domestic barriers, institutional barriers, community barriers, and course curriculum barriers. There are a total of 37 questions in the questionnaire.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study surveyed nursing students in Tacloban City and collected data using a questionnaire adopted from the study author Baticulon, et al. The respondents' profile variables included age, sex, religion, and monthly family income. The questionnaire addressed barriers to online learning, categorized into six parts: Technological, Individual, Domestic, Institutional, Community, and Course Curriculum Barriers. The data were analyzed using statistical methods such as Percentage, Mean, Pearson-r, and Eta correlation.

The results show that all nursing students in the study were adults, with the majority falling within the 20-39 years age range. Most respondents were female, Roman Catholic, and had a monthly income of 26-35k. Regarding barriers to online learning, nursing students expressed uncertainty about technological barriers and reported issues with internet connectivity and lack of familiarity with technical terms. They agreed that they faced individual barriers related to physical and mental health, as well as high costs of learning technology. They also highlighted administrative issues and lack of organization in the online learning curriculum as course curriculum barriers. Domestic barriers included family conflicts and daily household chores. Institutional barriers involved uncertainty in communicating with clinical instructors. Lastly, community barriers encompassed distractions caused by surrounding noise.

The study found significant relationships between the respondents' profile variables and certain barriers to online learning. Age, sex, and religion were associated with technological barriers. Age and religion were linked to individual barriers. Age and sex were connected to course curriculum barriers. Age, sex, and religion were associated with domestic barriers, while income was not. Age and religion showed a relationship with institutional barriers, whereas sex and income did not. Finally, sex and religion were related to community barriers, while age and income were not.

Conclusions

Based on the results the following conclusions were drawn.

1. All of the respondents were adults, majority of them were female, Roman Catholic and do have a family income of 26,000 – 35,000 per month.
2. Respondents agreed that individual, course curriculum, and community barriers affect online learning while they were unsure whether technological, institutional, and domestic barriers affect online learning.
3. The age variable does have a significant relationship with all the barriers to online learning.

Recommendations

This part of the study provides guidance on potential areas of further investigation or studies based on the findings and conclusions of an initial research study.

Explore the Impact of Technological Barriers: Conduct a detailed study to investigate the specific technological barriers faced by nursing students in Tacloban City during online learning. This research can delve into the specific technical terms they are unfamiliar with and assess the extent to which unreliable or absent internet connections hinder their learning experience.

Investigate Individual Barriers in Online Learning: Further examine the individual barriers to online learning identified in the study. Explore the physical and mental health issues faced by nursing students and their perceived high costs of learning technology. This research can focus on understanding the impact of these barriers on academic performance and explore potential interventions to address them.

Assess Course Curriculum Barriers: Conduct an in-depth analysis of the administrative issues and lack of organization in the online learning curriculum reported by nursing students. Investigate how these barriers affect their overall learning experience and identify strategies to enhance course curriculum design and implementation in online nursing education.

Explore Domestic Barriers: Conduct a comprehensive study to understand the specific domestic barriers faced by nursing students, such as family conflicts and daily household chores. This research can examine the impact of these barriers on their ability to engage effectively in online learning and suggest ways to provide support and resources to mitigate these challenges.

Investigate Institutional Support: Further examine the institutional barriers to online learning and their impact on nursing students. Specifically, explore the communication gaps between nursing students and their clinical instructors, and identify strategies to

improve communication channels and support mechanisms to address students' concerns and challenges.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethics is an integral part of conducting research, especially when the proponents are dealing with the people, the community, pertinent documents, animals, and the like. An absolute observance was done and followed by the ethical consideration in conducting this study to avoid fallacy or misconceptions of the participant's views about the phenomenon under study, its integrity, and most especially to protect them from any harm by hiding their personal information using John Doe names. Lastly, the proponent asked the approval of the consent form from the participants, stating their rights and privileges including their role in the research.

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